

The role of diketopiperazines in cooked cheese flavour

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Abstract

Diketopiperazines are cyclic dipeptides which impart bitterness and metallic flavour. They have previously been reported at subthreshold levels in raw cheese, but not studied in cooked cheese. Four diketopiperazines (cyclo-Pro-Pro, cyclo-Val-Pro, cyclo-Ala-Pro and cyclo-Leu-Pro) were detected in seven cooked cheeses (parmesan, mozzarella, and five different cheddars). Diketopiperazines were present in substantially higher concentrations in the cooked cheeses than their raw counterparts and were above bitter and metallic thresholds in some cooked samples. Diketopiperazine formation during cooking was higher in mature cheeses than in young cheeses, suggesting that aging cheeses produces precursors to diketopiperazine formation in the raw cheese.

Keywords: Diketopiperazine, cyclic peptide, bitterness, cheese

Introduction

Cheese is a major commodity produced by the dairy industry across Europe and globally. Mintel [1] estimates the UK market value for cheese to be £3.2 billion in 2020. Cheese is commonly used as an ingredient in cooked dishes (e.g. in fondue, as toppings to pizza or pasta, or grilled) with over 50% of cheese consumers reporting purchasing cheese for that purpose [2]. Despite the importance of ensuring good cheese flavour in cooked applications, most previous literature has only addressed raw cheese flavour.

Bitterness is typically regarded as a defect in cheese and, when detected in raw cheese, is thought to be a result of bitter peptides formed during proteolysis. Diketopiperazines (DKPs) are cyclic dipeptides which form in foods during fermentation and cooking. DKPs have been shown to contribute to bitter and metallic flavour [3]. While they have been reported previously in raw cheese, their concentrations were found to be subthreshold [4]. DKPs have also been reported in a number of cooked foods, including bread [5], chicken [6], cocoa [3] and coffee [7]. The aim of this work was to determine whether DKPs are formed in a range of cheeses during cooking, and whether the concentration of DKPs in cooked cheese is above bitter thresholds. Seven cheeses; mozzarella, parmesan and five cheddars were selected for this study to represent a range of cheeses typically used in cooked applications in the UK.

Experimental

Cheeses

Table: 1 List of cheeses used during the study.

Cheese	Abbreviation	Source	Aging period
Mozzarella	Mozz	Commercial *	<1 month **
Parmesan	Parm	Commercial *	> 2 years **
Mature cheddar	Ched	Commercial *	> 18 months **
High fat mild cheddar	HF	Reading pilot plant	3 months
Medium fat mild cheddar	MF	Reading pilot plant	3 months
Low fat mild cheddar	LF	Reading pilot plant	3 months
High fat 24 month aged cheddar	HF24	Reading pilot plant	24 months

* Commercially sourced (Sainsbury's supermarket, High Wycombe, UK). ** Typical aging period for this cheese variety

Cheese making

Milk was obtained from the University of Reading dairy herd of Holstein Friesians cows. Their diet (expressed per cow per day) comprised concentrate blend (9.5 kg), hay (1.0 kg), grass silage (19.0 kg), maize silage (24.0 kg), Trafford Gold (cow feed produced from wheat by-product) (4.0 kg), fat (0.1 kg), salt (0.1 kg), limestone flour (0.1 kg), minerals (0.03 kg). The milk was pasteurised at 73 °C for 15 s and skimmed. The resulting skimmed milk and cream were then recombined to produce 100 L each of low-fat milk (0.10 % fat), medium fat milk (2.7 % fat) and

high fat milk (3.9 % fat). The batches of milk were heated in cheese making vats at an initial pH of 6.75 to 30 °C, when 0.1 g/L starter culture R604 (Chr. Hansen, Hungerford UK) was added. Once the pH had dropped to 6.65, Chymosin, (CHYMAX, Chr. Hansen, Hungerford UK) was added to coagulate the milk. After 60 min the coagulum was cut at a pH of 6.60, after which the temperature was raised to 38 °C and held during the scalding phase, (approximately 90 min). Following the scalding, the whey was drained, and the curd was cheddared (sliced into small cubes to facilitate draining of the whey, before being stacked) for approximately 60 min at 38 °C until the pH reached 5.30. The curd was milled and salt added (2% w/w), then pressed in moulds for 24 h. The three curds were rested at 8 °C for 3 months, to give three mild cheddars. Additionally, a portion of the HF cheddar was ripened further to 24 months in total. The cheese was cut into approximately 250 g pieces, vacuum packed and stored at -20 °C until use. The final weights of high, medium and low-fat cheeses were 10.2, 8.8 and 6.2 kg respectively.

Cooking Procedure

Grated cheese (50 g) was spread evenly on a glass petri dish (90 mm diameter x 10 mm depth) and baked in a gas chromatograph oven (Hewlett Packard 5890 Series II) at 180 °C for 20 min. It was then cooled to room temperature, immersed in liquid nitrogen, and ground in a coffee grinder (Quest, Liverpool UK) to obtain a fine powder (30 s).

Extraction Method

Cheese (raw or cooked) (~50 g) was cut into 1cm³ pieces, immersed in liquid nitrogen, and ground in a coffee grinder (Quest, Liverpool UK) to obtain a fine powder. A portion of cheese (5 ± 0.1 g) was spiked with internal standard solution (50 µL 5-methyl-2-hexanone 0.500 % in isopropyl alcohol) and vortexed vigorously with 25 mL HPLC grade water for 60 min. The slurry was then centrifuged for 3 min at 2038 g and 15 °C. The supernatant underwent solid phase extraction using solid phase extraction (SPE) cartridges (Strata-X 33 µm polymeric reversed phase giga tube, Phenomenex, UK). The SPE cartridge was conditioned using 5 mL ethanol followed by 5 mL HPLC grade water. The sample was loaded slowly onto the cartridge and rinsed with a further 5 mL water and then dried by passing air through the cartridge for 30 s. The sample was then eluted from the cartridge slowly with 5 mL methyl acetate. All cooked cheeses were extracted in triplicate, while the raw cheeses were extracted once.

Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) parameters

Analyses were performed on an Agilent 7890-5977A GC-MS system (Agilent, Stockport, UK) equipped with an autosampler (Agilent, Stockport, UK). Each liquid extract (1 µL) was injected in splitless mode onto a DB-FFAP polar column (30 m 0.25 mm I.D., 0.25 mm film thickness), (Phenomenex, Macclesfield, UK). The oven temperature was 45 °C initially, rising by 4 °C/min to 220 °C, and held for 45 min. Helium was used as the carrier gas at 1.2 mL/min. The mass spectrometer was operated in EI mode with a source temperature of 230 °C, an ionising voltage of 70 eV, and a scan range from m/z 40 to m/z 300 at 5.3 scans/s. The data were acquired and analysed using Masshunter software (Version 4.5, Agilent, UK). Compounds were identified by comparing their mass spectra and linear retention indices with those of authentic standards (Bachem, Bubendorf, Switzerland).

Figure 1: Structures of four proline-containing DKPs detected in cooked cheese.

Results and discussion

Four DKPs were detected in cooked cheese. Their structures (shown in Figure 1) each included a proline moiety (cyclo(Val-Pro), cyclo(Leu-Pro), cyclo(Ala-Pro), cyclo(Pro-Pro)). Proline-containing DKPs are the most common category contributing approximately 90% of DKPs reported in foods [8, 9].

Figure 2: Concentration of four proline-containing DKPs in cooked and raw cheeses. Abbreviations: Parm (parmesan), Ched (mature cheddar), Mozz (mozzarella), HF (high fat mild cheddar), MF (medium fat mild cheddar), LF (low fat mild cheddar), HF24 (portion of HF which underwent 24 month aging). Metallic taste threshold represented by dashed line [3] and bitter taste threshold represented by a solid blue line [3]. Error bars show minimum and maximum range values.

DKP formation has been shown to occur from small peptides during cooking [8]. Otsuka et al [9] reported that when proline is one of the moieties in the precursor peptide, the two reacting atoms in DKP formation have a more favourable interatomic distance. This leads to more rapid formation of proline-containing DKPs than those containing other amino acids. Figure 2 shows the concentration of each DKP in the cooked and raw cheeses, along

with their metallic and bitter taste thresholds [3]. All DKPs detected were subthreshold in the raw cheeses. This agrees with previous analysis of raw Comte, which showed that DKPs were present at subthreshold concentrations in raw cheese and do not contribute to bitter taste [4].

The concentrations of DKPs increased substantially during cooking. Three DKPs were present above their bitter taste thresholds in the Ched and HF24 samples, and above their metallic thresholds in Parmesan. The DKP concentrations were similar between the HF, MF and LF cooked cheddar, demonstrating that the fat concentration in cheese did not influence the formation of DKPs when cooked.

In general, DKP concentration in cooked cheeses was higher in the matured cheeses than the milder cheeses. Comparison of HF and HF24 (the same cheese, differing only in maturation times of 3 and 24 months respectively) showed much higher concentrations of DKPs in cooked HF24 than HF, demonstrating that increased maturation time was associated with higher DKP concentration when cooked. As DKPs were not detected in either raw HF or HF24, this suggests that precursors to DKPs rather than DKPs themselves formed during cheese ripening.

Proline-containing-DKPs were recently found to form rapidly from di-and-tripeptides with proline in the second position from the N-terminal during heating [9]. This position favours rapid formation of DKPs compared to other similar peptides due to reduced steric hindrance around the atoms involved in the reaction. The process of proteolysis during cheese ripening generates small chain peptides and amino acids from cheese proteins [10]. It is likely that formation of proline containing di-and-tri peptides which are precursors to DKPs occurs during cheese ripening.

Conclusion

We report for the first time that DKPs are formed when cheese is cooked, and present at concentrations above taste thresholds in some cooked cheeses. Furthermore, DKP concentration in cooked (but not raw) cheeses increased with the duration of maturation. The process of proteolysis during cheese ripening is the most likely cause for this observation, as small chain peptides are DKP precursors. Future work in this area could look to confirm the sensory impact of DKP presence on cooked cheese flavour, and to determine whether the bitter and metallic thresholds differ for a high-fat matrix such as cheese to those previously reported for DKPs in water.

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